

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NFOR****FIRST NAME: ELVIS KILOH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 06****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord for 365)

ACA-401D QUIZ

1. According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2004), which of the following is NOT a reason why American English has become the dominant influence on "world English"?

- Population size of the U.S. compared to the U.K.
- Magnitude of the U.S. publishing industry
- Appeal of American popular culture
- Superiority of American educational institutions¹

2. What style guide does EUCLID recommend for formatting papers and citations?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024).

- APA Style
- MLA Style
- Chicago Manual of Style (Turabian)²**
- Harvard Style

3. **What is the primary purpose of research?**

- To gather as much information as possible
- To answer a question that others want to solve³**
- To prove a predetermined hypothesis
- To summarize existing knowledge

4. **Which of the following is NOT mentioned as a characteristic of a good research question?**

- It can be plausibly disproved
- Its answer would help understand a larger issue
- It requires resources within the researcher's capacity
- It can only be answered with quantitative data⁴**

5. **What do the readings suggest about working hypotheses in research?**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

⁴ Turabian, 27–28.

- They should be avoided to prevent bias
- They are only necessary for advanced researchers
- They help guide research but should be held lightly⁵**
- They should be finalized before data collection begins

6. **What is the main difference between practical and conceptual research problems?**

- Practical problems are more important than conceptual ones
- Conceptual problems focus on understanding, while practical problems focus on doing⁶**
- Practical problems are only relevant in professional settings
- Conceptual problems always lead to practical applications

7. **Which of the following is described as a primary source?**

- A scholarly journal article analyzing historical documents
- A textbook summarizing current knowledge in a field
- A literature review of recent research on a topic
- An original artifact or document from the period being studied⁷**

8. **What do the readings recommend for evaluating the reliability of an online source?**

⁵ Turabian, 31.

⁶ Turabian, 29.

⁷ Turabian, 36.

Checking if the site is sponsored by a reputable organization⁸

Trusting all sources equally

Only using sources from .edu domains

Avoiding all online sources in academic research

9. **What is the primary purpose of the Critical Analysis of Literature in a dissertation?**

To identify content and method gaps in prior research⁹

To summarize all existing research on the topic

To provide a historical overview of the field

To present the researcher's personal opinions on the topic

10. In quantitative research, what is the relationship between hypotheses and data analyses?

Hypotheses are derived from data analyses

Data analyses are guided directly by the hypotheses¹⁰

There is no direct relationship between hypotheses and data analyses

Hypotheses are only used in qualitative research

⁸ Turabian, 42.

⁹ James P. Jr Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 32.

¹⁰ Sampson, 35.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth edition. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.